

Clinical Study on the efficacy of Scalp Acupuncture in combination with Auriculotherapy in Rehabilitation of Stroke patients

Chodankar Shripad Ph. D. (Acupuncture)

Advance Acupuncture Forum, A-202, Mrud Kishor, Dattapada Road, Brorivali-W, Mumbai 400092, INDIA, Tel: +91 96190 59340, Email: shripad.chodankar@gmail.com

Abstract

Objective: The objectives of this study was to examine the long-term effects of repeated Scalp Acupuncture Treatment in combination with Auriculotherapy treatment on functional activities of daily living in post-acute stroke patients.

Design: This study was conducted in Treatment Camp organized in rural village area (440 km away from Mumbai). The treatment frequency was once in a month. General medical conditions are treated in this treatment camp. Seeing the amazing response in stroke patients, the retrospective study was conducted of the cases of Stroke patients

Patients: Patients of any gender, sex or ethnicity with ischemic or hemorrhagic stroke in the subacute or chronic phases were eligible. The total 59 cases were studied.

Main Outcome Measure: The Functional Coding Index was used to follow the efficacy of treatment. The details of Functional Coding Index are as per Annexure - 1

Results: The study was divided in three groups namely Speech affected, Upper Limb (UL) affected, and Lower Limb (LL) affected cases. In all three groups the Functional Coding Index improved significantly in 9 to 12 treatment sessions. This showed the significant functional recovery facilitating the patient's enhancement of Quality of Life.

Conclusions: The data suggest that the Chinese Scalp Acupuncture in combination with Auriculotherapy can achieve a very satisfactory effect in the treatment for the Rehabilitation of Stroke patients. This is very useful method to treat stroke patients and enhance their Quality of Life.

Registration: This was a retrospective study and it was not registered.

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Keywords

Stroke, Rehabilitation, Scalp Acupuncture, Auriculotherapy, Stroke rehabilitation

Introduction

Standard treatments in stroke rehabilitation are physiotherapy, occupational therapy, and speech therapy in addition to skilled medical and nursing care. Despite intensive inpatient rehabilitation in the stroke unit, more than 30% of acute stroke patients remain moderately to severely disabled at discharge. This reality drives people to search for other modalities of treatment (e.g., complementary and alternative therapies) in an attempt to further improve the outcome of stroke rehabilitation.

Acupuncture has been used for stroke in China and Korea for centuries but in the last few decades some new forms of acupuncture were developed. One of these is Chinese Scalp Acupuncture.

This study was conducted in Treatment Camp organized in rural village area (440 km away from Mumbai). The treatment frequency was once in a month.

General medical conditions are treated in this treatment camp. Seeing the amazing response, the retrospective study was conducted of the cases of Stroke patients, which is presented herewith.

The total 59 cases were studied.

The patients in this area do not have adequate financial resources for their treatment and/or investigations. As such the conventional diagnostic investigations such as blood report, MRI, CT scan were not available of the subject cases. However, the diagnosis as per TCM and Auriculotherapy were performed for all the cases.

Method

Chinese Scalp Acupuncture was selected as the treatment method for the cases of Stroke patients. The normal recommended treatment frequency for scalp acupuncture is twice a week. Since the treatments were done at the monthly camps (treatment frequency once a month), the treatment of stroke patients with scalp acupuncture was combined with Auriculotherapy since the Auriculotherapy has following salient features.

- Simple for application
- Cost effective
- No side effects
- Does not require frequent visits
- It regulates the function

The Functional Coding Index was used to follow the efficacy of treatment. The details of Functional Coding Index are as per Annexure - 1

The diagnosis of the patients was performed as per TCM and Auriculotherapy postulate.

For the scalp acupuncture, the scalp areas viz. Motor area, sensory area, speech area, praxis area and Foot Motor Sensory Area (FMSA Area) were selected and needled based on functional disability.

For Auriculotherapy, the following procedure is followed and on this basis the ear points were selected and applied.

Diagnosis

Treatment Protocol

1. The treatment session was done with the frequency of once a month.
2. During the treatment session, first, the patient was treated with Scalp Acupuncture and then subsequently treated with Auriculotherapy.
3. In scalp acupuncture session, the scalp area viz. Motor area, sensory area, speech area, and praxis area are needled and retained for 30 minutes and then removed.
4. In Auriculotherapy session, the selected auricular points are treated with dual vaccaria seeds.
5. The applied seeds are to be maintained by the patients for a period of one month. However, it was observed that the seeds are normally maintained for a period of 21 to 30 days after application.
6. The applied individual seeds are to be pressed (stimulated) manually three time a day, by the patients.
7. The applied seeds are to be protected from the soaking of the water.
8. The total cases registered were 59. Refer Table 1 and Table 2, for the differentiation of the cases based on age group and time after when treatment started respectively.

Table 1: Differentiation based on Age group

Age Group	Total	Male	Female
< 25	1	0	1
25 - 45	15	13	2
45 - 65	36	35	1
65 & above	7	4	3
Total	59	52	7

Table 2: Differentiation based on time after when treatment started

Time after when treatment started	Age group				
	Total	< 25	25 - 45	45 - 65	> 65
Less than 1 year	19	0	7	10	2
1 to 5 years	30	0	7	19	4
More than 5 years	10	1	1	7	1
Total	59	1	15	36	7

Result

Study: No of cases 59

Cases of speech affected

There were 34 speech affected cases out of total 59 cases. Refer Table 3 for the differentiation based on speech score and Table 4 for Results of speech affected cases.

Table 3: Differentiation based on speech score

Speech Score	Cases
0	12
1	6
2	3
3	14

Table 4: Result of Speech affected cases

Speech score	Cases	No. of cases Improved to			
		Score 1	Score 2	Score 3	Score 4
0	12	1	2	7	2
1	6	-	-	3	3
2	3	-	-	1	2
3	14	-	-	1	13

- 1) From score 0: (9/12) 75% reached to functional score of 3 & 4 in 6 - 9 treatment sessions
(2/12) 16% achieved normal speech
- 2) From score 1 & 2: (9/9) 100% reached to functional score of 3 & 4
(5/9) 55% achieved normal speech
- 3) From score 3: (13/14) 93% achieved normal speech in 6 treatment sessions
Out of this (12/13) achieved in 6 treatment sessions and (1/13) achieved in 9 treatment session

Maximum improvement for all score group achieved within 6 - 9 treatment sessions.

Total improvement for 0 - 2 score

- 1) To functional level was (18/21) 85%
- 2) To absolute normal level was (7/21) 33%

Cases of Upper Limb (UL) affected

There were 52 Upper Limb affected cases out of total 59 cases. Refer Table 5 for the differentiation based on UL score and Table 6 for Results of UL affected cases.

Table 5: Differentiation based on UL score

UL score	Total
0	23
1 - 10	29
Total	52

Table 6: Result of UL affected cases

UL score	Total	No. of cases Improved to				
		No Change	1-5	6-10	10-13	14-15
0	23	1	9	6	3	4
1-10	29	2	-	6	12	9
Total	52	3	9	12	15	13

- 1) From score 0: (13/23) 57% patients showed good improvement with score >5
(7/23) 30% patients showed functional improvement >10
(4/23) 17% patients showed functionally normal >14
- 2) From score 1-10: (21/29) 72% patients showed functional improvement >10
(9/29) 31% patients showed functionally normal >14

Maximum improvement for all score group achieved within 9 - 12 treatment sessions.

Cases of Lower Limb (LL) affected

There were 39 Lower Limb affected cases out of total 59 cases. Refer Table 7 for the differentiation based on LL score and Table 8 for Results of LL affected cases.

Table 7: Differentiation based on LL score

LL score	Total
0	10
1-2	23
3	6
Total	39

Table 8: Result of LL affected cases

LL score	Total	No. of cases Improved to			
		No Change	Up to 2	3 or 4	5
0	10	-	3	3	4
1-2	23	3	-	15	5
3	6	1	-	4	1
Total	39	4	3	22	10

- 1) From score 0: (7/10) 70% reached to functional score of 3 - 5
(4/10) 40% achieved normal function
- 2) From score 1 & 2: (20/23) 87% reached to functional score of 3 - 5
(5/23) 22% achieved normal function
- 3) From score 3: (5/6) 83% reached to functional score of 4 - 5
(1/6) 17% achieved normal function

In 6 - 9 treatment sessions

(32/39) 82% achieved functional improvement

(10/39) 26% achieved normal function

Discussion

Scalp Area / Ear Point Selection

On Scalp: (Selection of area based on symptoms) Motor Area, Sensory Area, FMSA, Praxis, Speech area (in case of speech affected).

Points on ear (ipsilateral to the side of clinical sensory or motor deficit)

On the lateral ear: Master sensory (eye) point, Brainstem point, and Thalamus.

On the medial ear: Master motor point, and the upper and lower spinal cord motor points, Synthesis point.

On either ear: Liver, Spleen, Kidney, Heart, and Laterality

Location of Scalp Area

1. Motor area

The Motor Area is located on the area of the scalp corresponding to the pre-central gyrus of the frontal lobe. The Motor Area is located in a strip beginning at the midline at a point 0.5 cm posterior to the previously located midpoint of the head, along the anterior-posterior line. The Motor Area runs from this point obliquely down to the point where the eyebrow-occipital line intersects the anterior hairline (Fig. 1 Scalp Area (Motor Area, Speech Area, Praxis Area) - Stroke Rehab). The line of the Motor Area determines the angle and location of several other areas, such as the Sensory Area and Chorea and Tremor Area.

The Motor Area is divided into three regions according to the homunculus projection. In order to correctly locate these three regions, the whole Motor Area is divided equally into fifths. Then three regions are measured as follows: upper one-fifth (1/5) region, middle two-fifths (2/5) region, and lower two-fifths (2/5) region (Fig. 1 Scalp Area (Motor Area, Speech Area, Praxis Area) - Stroke Rehab).

The upper 1/5 region is used to treat contralateral dysfunctional movement of the lower extremity, trunk, spinal cord, and neck.

The middle 2/5 region is used to treat contralateral dysfunctional movement of the upper extremity.

The lower 2/5 region is used to treat bilateral dysfunctional movement of the face and head. It is also an effective area for treating dysphasia due to stroke and other brain damage. This is also called as 'First Speech Area'

2. Speech I Area

There are three speech areas. Speech I Area is located on the posterior third of the gyrus frontalis inferior over the frontal lobe and controls groups of muscles for speech and phonation. This Area corresponds to Broca's area of the frontal lobe, which controls the muscles of the tongue and mouth that form speech. Speech I Area overlaps the lower 2/5 of the Motor Area (Fig. 1 Scalp Area (Motor Area, Speech Area, Praxis Area) - Stroke Rehab).

3. Speech II Area

This area lies over the reading and comprehension part of the parietal lobe, and is located by finding the parietal tubercle. From the parietal tubercle, run a line parallel to the anterior-posterior line 2 cm posteriorly. Using this as the starting point, the Speech 2 Area runs 3 cm in length, parallel to the anterior posterior line (Fig. 1 Scalp Area (Motor Area, Speech Area, Praxis Area) - Stroke Rehab).

This area is used for nominal aphasia – the inability to name objects. In this disorder, the patient can describe an object, but cannot produce the noun.

Fig. 1: Scalp Area (Motor Area, Speech Area, Praxis Area) - Stroke Rehab

4. Speech III Area

This overlies Wernicke's area of the temporal lobe, and overlaps the posterior half of the Vertigo and Hearing Area. It lies on the same horizontal line 1.5 cm superior to the apex of the auricle but begins at the midpoint of the Vertigo and Hearing Area directly above the auricle and runs 4 cm posteriorly (Fig. 1 Scalp Area (Motor Area, Speech Area, Praxis Area) - Stroke Rehab).

It is used for treatment of receptive aphasia, where the patient can articulate words but the words don't make sense.

5. Praxis Area (Usage Area, Application Area)

Starting from the parietal tubercle, the Praxis Area joins 3 lines, one running straight downward and the other two at a 40-degree angle anterior and posterior to the vertical line (Fig. 1 Scalp Area (Motor Area, Speech Area, Praxis Area) - Stroke Rehab).

This area is for apraxia; the inability to execute certain fine motor activities such as buttoning a shirt.

6. Foot Motor and Sensory Area (FMSA Area)

The FMSA is located parallel to the anterior-posterior line, 1 cm lateral to the midline beginning at the level of the midpoint of the anterior-posterior line and running 4 cm posteriorly (Fig. 2 Foot Motor Sensory Area (FMSA Area) - Stroke Rehab). The Foot Motor and Sensory Area gets its name from including both the Motor Area and the Sensory Area in the region of the foot on the homunculus.

Fig. 2: Foot Motor Sensory Area (FMSA Area) - Stroke Rehab

Location of Ear points

Refer Fig. 3 Selection of Points - Stroke Rehab

Fig. 3: Selection of Points - Stroke Rehab

Conclusion

The data suggest that the Chinese Scalp Acupuncture in combination with Auriculotherapy can achieve a very satisfactory effect in the treatment for the Rehabilitation of Stroke patients in 9 to 12 treatment sessions.

After looking at the results of the above cases, the control study may help further to get more clarity on the subject.

Bibliography

1. Handbook to Auriculotherapy by P.M.F. Nogier
2. Auriculotherapy by Raphael Nogier
3. Auricular Medicine by Dr. Li-Chun Huang
4. Article: Auriculotherapy in Neurology by Dr. Gary Stanton
5. Head-Needle Therapy by Dr. Anton Jayasuriya
6. Chinese Scalp Acupuncture by Jason Jishun Hao & Linda Lingzhi Hao

Annexure - 1

Functional Coding Index

	Max. score	Score	Description
Speech	4	0	Can understand but cannot speak
		1	Can express but no speech
		2	Speech - voice only but not relevant
		3	Slurred speech
		4	Normal speech
Shoulder	4	0	No movement
		1	Partial movement but not purposeful
		2	slight purposeful movement
		3	can move on own
		4	Normal movement
Elbow	4	0	No movement
		1	Partial movement but not purposeful
		2	slight purposeful movement
		3	can move on own
		4	Normal movement
Wrist	4	0	No movement
		1	Partial movement but not purposeful
		2	slight purposeful movement
		3	can move on own
		4	Normal movement
Fingers	3	0	No movement
		1	can grip
		2	can write
		3	can do buttoning
Back (Hip)	2	0	cannot sit
		1	can sit with support
		2	can sit without support
Leg	2	0	cannot walk
		1	can walk with support
		2	can walk without support
Foot	1	0	cannot wear footwear on own
		1	can wear footwear